

METHODS OF MORAL EDUCATION FOR PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract:

One of the important tasks facing preschool pedagogy is to improve the methods of providing spiritual and moral education to preschool children. In this work, the methods of providing moral education to preschool children, the role of the family in making them a well-rounded person in the future are considered.

Keywords:

Ethics, spiritual and moral education, mental education, methods of moral education, means of moral education.

Since ancient times, philosophers, scientists, parents, writers and teachers have been interested in the issue of moral education of the next generation. Let's not hide that each older generation determines that the moral foundations of the youth have declined. Regularly, new recommendations are being developed, their purpose is to increase the level of morals. Moral education is an important component of the comprehensive development of a person. It is a process aimed at inculcating moral ideas and knowledge in children, educating them about moral feelings and qualities of a person, positive attitudes and culture of behavior.

In the process of moral education, the child matures morally. In the process of developing moral ideas, first of all, they begin to consciously understand their relationships with others, moral lessons develop in their relationships with peers and adults.

The traditions, lifestyle, education and cultural traditions of the Uzbek people go back to the distant centuries. The people of our current and future generations should know Uzbek national spirituality well and follow it. Only then will the society be full, prosperous, and people will live a peaceful and cultural life.

The task and content of moral education of preschool children requires education and development of the child's spiritual world, his mind, moral feelings, personal qualities and behavior. The tasks of moral education are mainly the following:

- Education of moral feelings, ideas and behavior in children;
- Education of moral culture and positive relations;
- Cultivating moral feelings in a person;
- Elimination of negative feelings in behavior.

These general tasks are concretized according to age groups and are reflected in the content of the educational process. It is important to use various methods and methods in providing moral education to preschool children. Moral education methods are activities aimed at acquiring moral imagination and knowledge of children, cultural behavior and positive relations, moral feelings and qualities of a person. Methods of moral education are divided into such types as methods aimed at forming moral awareness, i.e. moral imagination and

knowledge, the desire to fulfill them, methods aimed at forming cultural behavior and positive relations, auxiliary methods aimed at stimulating moral feelings and relations. divided.

There are also dual methods of moral education - self-education: persuasion and self-conviction (intellectual sphere), encouragement and motivation (motivational sphere), suggestion and self- self-hypnosis (emotional domain), demand and exercise (voluntary domain), correction and self-correction (self-regulatory domain), situational training and social testing (subject-practical domain) , dilemma method and reflection (existential field). These methods are the most effective in the process of moral education in our time. No matter how good the methods are, they only work under certain conditions.

We must not forget that any method should be humane, not discriminate against the child, and not violate his rights. The method must be realistic, feasible, it requires a logical conclusion. To use the method, it is necessary to prepare the conditions and tools in advance. The method should not be applied in the same way to all children and in all situations. Teaching methods should be used with tact. The child should not feel that he is being disciplined. When choosing methods, it is necessary to take into account the level of complexity of the quality being formed.

When designing and choosing methods, it is important to anticipate the possible results of their impact on a particular child. Applying the methods of moral education requires patience and tolerance. When it comes to a preschooler, you can't count on immediate and permanent results. Realizing that the result will not be achieved immediately, it is necessary to repeat the already used methods and choose new ones, and perhaps not in the form and quality that we planned. Moral education of preschool children should be dominated by practical methods related to teaching the child how to act. If you rely only on consciousness, if you understand the importance of positive behavior and if you do not teach such behavior methods, there will be no results. The methods are used not separately, but in addition and interconnected. The basis for choosing the methods that can and should be used together is the leading educational task and the age of the children. In the pedagogical literature, the concept of the form of education is defined as a method of organizing the educational process.

Thus, in order for children to acquire moral ideas and concepts and turn them into a daily habit, intensive activities of children under the guidance of adults should be organized. The educator uses all means and methods to educate moral feelings in the child, because only then can he teach examples of good behavior.

References:

1. Lectures and speeches of our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev;
2. The Law "On Preschool Education" of Uzbekistan 2020
3. F. Kadirova, Sh. Toshpolatova "Pedagogy before school" T. "Spirituality" 2013
4. R. Yusupova "Pedagogy of preschool education" T. "Teacher" 1993
5. O. Hasanboyeva "Pedagogy of preschool education". T. "Ilm Ziya" 2006
6. Sh. Sodikova "Pedagogy before school" "T. Reflections" 2013
7. N.M. Kayumova "Preschool pedagogy" T "TDPU" publishing house 2013